

Teaching Competencies and Performance Evaluation of Physical Education Teachers in the Intermediate Education Stage in the Western Mountain Region, Libya

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ABSTRACT

The current study aimed at identifying the teaching competencies and evaluating the performance of physical education teachers in the intermediate education stage in the Western Mountain region in Libya in terms of competencies (teaching methods - implementation), where the researcher used the descriptive approach in addition to using a questionnaire form which consisted of (28) paragraphs as a study tool. The community consisted of all teachers of each of (Gharyan-Al-Asabaa-Kikla) in the Western Gabal region, whose number was (113) teachers, and the study sample consisted of (60) teachers. It is ahead of the adequacy of implementation, which was 66%, and to a large degree for each of them.

Keywords: Teaching competencies, implementation, teaching methods

INTRODUCTION

The rapid change in all areas of life is the distinguishing feature of our current era and as a result of these

changes it was necessary to respond to them through changing the functions of institutions of all kinds and forms, and physical education represents a process of directing the growth of individuals and their readiness, preferences, activities and recruitment to serve the community and it is the framework that embodies the philosophy and needs of society to reach To the desired goals (Al-Ahmad, 2005, p. 14).

The cognitive and scientific growth has doubled several times in the last few decades of the century, and the

Access this article online

Website:
<http://sjsr.se/>

ISSN:
2001-9211

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scientific revolution was not associated with theoretical aspects only, but rather extended to the applied and scientific fields. Education was not isolated from these changes that occurred, but rather contributed to them and sought to benefit from them and interact with them in order to create The desired change in the behavior of the individual, and the work to find modern concepts consistent with scientific progress, and the tremendous knowledge explosion, in enriching the experiences and skills of those in charge of education so that they can positively influence the behavior of learners (Al-Sayeh, 2002, 23).

And when it is impossible for such a change to occur except with good and qualitative education, modern education has sought to pay attention to the educational structure to become more flexible and responsive to rapid changes and to train teachers to accept this change, and this requires the continuous renewal of teachers 'and students' information alike at various levels and stages of education, and keeping pace with progress And the technological development of the world for the optimum utilization of the available human and natural resources (Merai, 2003, 18).

This began with the interest in preparing the teacher and training him to understand the changes of the age and adapt to the new role assigned to him. The educational process is of no value if its field is devoid of the competent teacher who is able to assume his responsibilities, so the teacher's personality, educational competencies, motivation, and the ability of a specialized subject, and his method of organizing the appropriate educational environment depends on The training programs he receives to acquire skills related to teaching methods (Zaitoun, 2005, p. 36).

The teacher's role in any educational system depends on a set of interrelated factors that form the frame of reference for the concept of the educational process. Whatever concepts differ for the role of the teacher, it remains a decisive factor in the success or failure of the educational process, because the teacher's job is no longer a mechanical process limited to transferring knowledge to learners. Rather, it represents an effective tool in developing the learners' mental, social, and physical abilities, and in developing their personalities in general (Sukkar and Khazindar, 2005, p.57).

Modern philosophies of education have focused on the necessity of preparing the teacher in a preparation

that enables him to use the information, concepts, principles, skills, trends and values he has learned in his daily life on the one hand, and on the necessity of preparing him in order to learn continuously, in a better and greater manner than the topics he learned and on other new topics. (Kamal, Abdulaziz, 2003, p.20).

Therefore, preparing the teacher and preparing him for the demands of the profession and the requirements of the age is one of the matters that receive constant attention in all educational systems, as the teacher is the cornerstone of the educational process, and the level of the teacher and the extent of effectiveness that he is characterized by during the performance of his educational mission are what determine the quality of education and the extent of achieving educational goals.

And since physical education is one of the elements of public education, reaching global levels in it is a manifestation of the state's civilized progress, and an indicator of its social and economic advancement. Physical education causes emotional and social changes in personality as well as the physical changes that arise from physical exercise and playing sports. (El-Sawi and Darwish, 1990).

In light of this lofty view of the position of physical education in the educational system, the need for preparing a physical education teacher in an educational and professional manner increases to the extent that it makes him effective in performing the teaching process, and has a serious interest in the teaching profession and creates a personality capable of interacting with the various social issues and situations in which he exists to achieve The goals of physical education, especially in light of the lack of attention to which the profession is exposed, threatening its position among other educational fields (Sweiss, 1991).

Therefore, the physical education teacher must be provided with the programs and experiences and the opportunities that must be prepared for him through programs developed on scientific grounds, with clear and specific educational goals, and to have the opportunity to exploit all his abilities and capabilities in order to achieve his goals and reach satisfactory and fruitful results. (Khasawneh, 2002).

And then the current study seeks to identify the teaching competencies and evaluate the performance

of physical education teachers at the intermediate education stage in the Western Mountain region in Libya, out of concern for preparing the teacher and training him to understand the changes of the era and adapt to the new role assigned to him, as the teacher is considered a messenger of culture and calling for reform and renewal. And innovation and development, it is on his shoulders the responsibility to prepare, care for, train and direct future generations. The educational process is of no value if its field is devoid of an efficient teacher who is able to assume his responsibilities. That he receives to acquire skills specific to teaching methods.

SEARCH PROBLEM

The effectiveness of educational institutions depends directly on the sufficiency of the teacher, if the teacher is the organizer and facilitator of the student's education process. Therefore, raising the teacher's sufficiency is one of the goals of the educational institution. Educational competencies are among the basic requirements for teachers, in order to make the educational process successful. Studies in the educational and mathematical fields by studying the educational competencies of teachers (Khawaldeh, 1990).

Many physical education experts believe that those in charge of teaching physical education in the intermediate education stage must possess specific educational competencies that qualify them to teach various sports skills efficiently and effectively, in addition to the personal competencies of these teachers, and there is no doubt that teachers' possession of educational competencies will develop their abilities, enrich their experiences and help them to Achieving educational goals, so disclosing their availability to them is very important, because it will help to identify their weaknesses and strengths, and then address them (Al-Khouli, Anan and Jalloun, 1994).

The researcher noticed through his contact with the educational milieu that there was a weakness in the performance of physical education teachers, which prompted him to this study to determine and evaluate the educational competencies that must be available to physical education teachers in this educational stage in particular and for other educational stages in general, because of this educational stage of A significant impact on the development of the student's personality,

a comprehensive and balanced development in all different aspects of life. These educational competencies also help the teacher in mastering the teaching of physical education and raising his level of competence in his performance, the effect of which is evident in the educational process as a whole.

Recently, there has been an increase in interest in teaching competencies by researchers and educators with the aim of improving the effectiveness of teachers and developing their educational and teaching competencies. Recent studies and research unite that there are shortcomings in the teaching competencies required to be available to the teacher, which has been effectively reflected on the educational and academic performance of students.

Therefore, this study comes in line with modern educational trends that focus on teaching and educational competencies in preparing and training teachers. Therefore, this research is a serious attempt in order to identify and evaluate the teaching and educational competencies necessary for physical education teachers in the cities of the Western Mountain in Libya.

Based on the aforementioned, the current study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the necessary competencies for physical education teachers in the intermediate education stage in the Western Mountain Region (Gharyan - Al-Asabaa - Kikla) from their point of view within the field of teaching methods?
2. What are the necessary competencies for physical education teachers in the intermediate education stage in the Western Jabal Region (Gharyan - Al-Asabaa - Kikla) from their point of view within the field of implementation?

The importance of studying:

1. Neutralizing the teaching competencies of physical education teachers.
2. Determine the relative importance of the competencies of teaching and implementation methods.

Fields of Study

The researcher suggests applying the study through three areas as follows:

1. The human field: Physical education teachers in the Western Mountain region.

2. Spatial domain: middle education schools in the Western Mountain region.
3. Temporal domain: during the academic year 2019-2020.

Defining Terms

Competency

It is the amount of knowledge, convictions, and skills an individual attains that enable him to perform related to the task entrusted to him, and it also refers to the state of the individual possessing the appropriate ability to perform a specific duty (Webster, 1968.P.213).

(Anderson, 1996, p. 30) defines that it is a set of knowledge, concepts, skills, and attitudes that a teacher acquires as a result of his preparation in a specific program during and before service, which directs the teaching behavior and improves the level of his performance.

Teaching competency

It is the set of teaching knowledge and skills that make the teacher able to perform his profession within appropriate specifications that number institutions can form among students. (Baquer, 1991, p. 7).

It is also defined as acquired capabilities that allow behavior and action in a specific context, and its content consists of knowledge, abilities, skills, and trends that are integrated in a complex way, and the individual who acquired them raises, recruits and employs them with the intention of confronting a problem and solving it in a specific situation (Al-Darj, 2000).

(Mustafa Al-Sayeh, 2001, p. 83) defines it as the entirety of the behavior and behavior of a physical education teacher, which includes knowledge and attitudes during and outside the educational situation. This behavior is characterized by a high level of performance and accuracy.

THE STUDY OF MUDAR ABDUL-BAQI, ET AL. (1999)

Title: Teaching competencies of teachers of physical education in the provinces of the central Euphrates in Iraq.

The study aimed to determine the educational competencies of middle school physical education

teachers, while determining the relative importance of each sufficiency of competencies, and the researchers used the descriptive approach in the survey method to suit the nature of the problem of the subject of study, on a sample that included teachers of physical education for the middle school stage in the provinces of the Middle Euphrates In a random method consisting of (120) teachers and physical education schools, the researchers also used the questionnaire as a tool to complete the requirements of the study and distributed the open questionnaire to a number of experts, and the study found that there are individual differences between teachers of physical education as described by the researchers in their study through the teaching competencies that It should be characterized by physical education teachers, (adequacy of lesson preparation and implementation, scientific competence, professional growth and ethics, adequacy of the human relationship, adequacy of order in the classroom and finally adequacy of assessment), and the basic educational competencies are necessary for teachers of physical education, which must be used as a standard for the teacher. Competence.

THE STUDY OF MUHAMMAD BIN ABDULLAH MUHAMMAD ASIRI (2001)

The extent of the importance of the educational competencies needed for a physical education teacher in the middle school in Riyadh

The study aimed to identify the extent of the importance of the educational competencies needed for a physical education teacher in the middle stage from the point of view of the faculty, supervisors and teachers of physical education in Riyadh. The study sample consisted of the entire population of the study.

The results of the study show that (83) adequacy of the educational competencies included in the study tool are of great importance to the physical education teacher and represent (97%) of the total educational competencies. Also, the sample members see that (3) important competencies of a moderate degree, representing (3%) of the total Educational competencies, and no sufficiency of educational competencies obtained a degree of little or no importance, and the sample members arranged axes of educational competencies according to their importance, as follows: the axis of competencies related

to human relations, the axis of competencies related to professional growth, the axis of competencies related to the implementation of the lesson, the axis of competencies related to preparing the lesson, the axis of competencies related to the evaluation of the lesson, the axis of competencies.

Related to personality, and the results also found that there are no statistically significant differences among the study sample according to the job variable, and years of experience in the axes of educational competencies, except for the competency axis related to preparing the lesson.

FATHI RUSHDIE (2002)

Entitled (Proposing the Performance Efficiency Evaluation Card for the Physical Education Teacher in the First Stage of Basic Education), the study aims to propose the Performance Efficiency Evaluation Card for the Physical Education teacher in the first stage of basic education. The study was conducted on a random sample of physical education teachers consisting of (62) teachers., And the researcher used the descriptive approach, and the most important results were that there is a positive correlation between the teacher's performance competency and the students' performance level.

A STUDY (DAWOOD AL-JANABI, 2002)

Entitled "Teaching competencies required for middle school chemistry teachers and their relationship to the achievement incentive of their students", which aimed to define a list of teaching competencies needed for middle school chemistry teachers and to identify the teaching competencies of middle school chemistry teachers and their relationship to their students' achievement incentive, and the research sample reached (51) teachers and schools, while the sample of students reached (1070) male and female students of the second intermediate grade, and the researcher prepared an observation form that included (90) competencies distributed over (17) fields, and the researcher concluded that the benefit from the list of teaching competencies that were identified in the goal The study by those involved in the performance and evaluation of the performance of chemistry teachers before and during the service, and the need for teachers to be able to teach instructional planning

and the elements of the daily plan and to ensure that it is implemented during the lesson.

STUDY PROCEDURES

Study Approach

The researcher used the descriptive method with the survey method, due to its suitability to the nature of this study, and because the survey method describes what is an object and explains it with determining its causes.

Study Population

Information on the research community was obtained from the Educational Inspection Department in the three municipalities, in terms of the number of teachers, which amounted to (113) teachers, as well as the number of schools and their locations in the city.

Research Sample

The sample of the study consisted of (60) physical education teachers who were randomly selected from the original community from the three schools located within the municipalities of each of (Gharyan - Al Asaba - Kikla) by one school from each municipality in the Western Jabaal region.

Research tool: In order to achieve the research objectives, it was required to build a measure of teaching competencies according to the following steps:

The design of the scale: for the inappropriateness of previous research measures (tool) with the research topic in terms of objectives and the lack of a ready-made tool as far as the researcher knows The researcher designed a (instrument) scale according to the following steps:

Access to the literature and sources: - After the researcher examined the literature and conditions for building the questionnaire, as well as previous studies on the research topic, the researcher relied on the questionnaire as a tool to collect information and reach the research objectives.

The initial design of the scale: The researcher presented an open questionnaire containing the title, the concept of teaching competencies and the seven axes to a group of university professors with a specialization in teaching methods and curricula to define and write

the paragraphs of the teaching competencies that must be provided in the physical education teacher in the middle stage, with the deletion, modification or addition Any of the axes, and the form included in its initial form (30) paragraphs distributed into two areas, namely:

1. Implementation efficiencies
2. The competencies of teaching methods.

After the researcher presented the initial form to (6) experts who hold a doctorate in the field of teaching methods and curriculum science, the amendments were approved by the experts and the expressions that they did not agree upon were deleted Table 1. The form was finalized, which contained (26) phrases which were completed. Apply them to the individuals of the study sample.

Based on the review of previous studies, the following percentages were adopted in interpreting the results:

1. 80% and above is a very large degree of sufficiency
2. 70-79% is high adequacy
3. 60-69% is a moderate degree of sufficiency
4. 50-59% is low adequacy
5. Less than 50% low sufficiency.

The validity of the tool: The researcher relied on extracting the apparent truthfulness by presenting the tool to a group of specialists in the field of teaching methods, and the researcher relied on the percentage of arbitrators' agreement (75%) and more standard for the validity of paragraphs, and in light of expert opinions, the researcher rearranged and reformulated the paragraphs and deleted the paragraphs that did not It gets a high rate of opinions and other paragraphs amendment. The total of the deleted paragraphs was (16) paragraphs, and the discriminatory honesty was extracted through statistical procedures, and the tool was applied in its initial form on a sample of (20) teachers, and because the sample was small, the forms were divided into two groups with high degrees and low degrees and rates of (50%) For high scores and (50%) for low scores.

Self-honesty: It is a type of validity that refers to the square root of the reliability coefficient, and this type of validity is based on experimental grades after eliminating measurement errors, meaning that the self or real truthfulness expresses what the test contains is a fact of the characteristic that it measures free of any errors or defects. Meaning the amount of saturation of the scale really.

It was calculated by finding the square root of the values of the Cronbach alpha stability coefficients for the current list in terms of its dimensions and the total degree, and the following table illustrates this.

It is evident from the table that the current list is highly self-truthful.

RESULTS

Presenting and interpreting the results in light of the findings of the research, which are as follows:

It is evident from Table 2 that the teaching competencies necessary for physical education teachers, which must be used as a criterion for a competent teacher in the intermediate education stage, have been limited to two main areas, namely (the field of implementation and the field of teaching methods) as it is clear from the table (1) that the teaching competencies of physical education teachers It came as follows:

1. First place: the efficiencies of teaching methods, with a percentage (75.21%), with a degree of adequacy.
2. The second place: implementation efficiencies at a rate of (72.31%) with a high degree of adequacy

As for the total degree of competencies, it came to a large degree and with a percentage of (73.25%) and with a great degree of sufficiency, and through the results that were achieved for the first objective of the study, the researcher reached a list of basic teaching competencies for physical education teachers, which should be used as a standard for an efficient teacher. Limiting it to two areas, and each field has a number of teaching competencies.

The researcher believes that these results give a picture of the reality of physical education in the school curriculum and the current reality of the teaching competencies of physical education teachers in some intermediate education schools in the Western Mountain region.

Table 1: The teaching competencies for physical education teachers

Total degree	Teaching Methods	Implementation	Areas of competencies
0.847	0.789	0.854	Cronbach Alpha Laboratories

To answer the second question, which states: What are the teaching competencies required for physical education teachers in the Western Mountain region from their point of view within the field of implementation?

Table 3 shows the arithmetic averages and percentages of the responses of physical education teachers to a paragraph of the field of implementation, as the percentage of physical education teachers for this field was large over the first four paragraphs, as the percentage of responses ranged between (70% to 78%) and it was medium. On the rest of the paragraphs, with the exception of the last paragraph, where the percentage of responses ranged between 61% - 69%), while the overall score for the field was medium and the percentage of response was (66%).

As it is evident from the previous table that the study sample of physical education teachers have paid attention to the competencies related to the field of implementation of the lesson and confirmed that the

success of the physical education lesson depends entirely on the good implementation of the teacher for the lesson and this comes through the teacher's possession of the teaching and educational competencies of the teacher's implementation of the lesson and follow-up skills. The levels of students, equipment and tools used, how to use them, what physical education is studied and the extent of its connection, and what the ministry does through educational directorates and school activity departments to hold specialized professional courses for teachers on an ongoing basis may be one of the reasons that help the teacher to develop himself professionally in addition to the nature of the curriculum. Applied physical education, which requires the availability of the necessary capabilities and tools, which may not be available in all schools in general in the Western Mountain region, the reason for most of the field's paragraphs obtaining an intermediate degree.

To answer the second question of the study, which states: What teaching competencies are needed for

Table 2: Shows the arithmetic means and percentages for the two fields of study. The fields of teaching competencies, the number of paragraphs, the arithmetic mean, the percentages, the estimate

Appreciation	Percentages	Arithmetic mean	Number of paragraphs	The teaching competencies
High	72.31 %	3.32	13	Execution area
High	75.21 %	3.51	13	Teaching methods

Table 3: Arithmetic averages and percentages of the teaching competencies of physical education teachers for the field of implementation

Adequacy of the field of implementation	Mean	The percentage	The score
Uses appropriate educational methods for students	3.67	78%	High
The ability to explain verbal and movement with students during the lesson is great	3.62	75%	High
Encouraging students to express their opinion about the lesson about new, unclear skills.	3.49	70%	High
The ability to link the current and previous lesson to consolidate the skill by preparing the review	3.32	70%	High
The course material is presented clearly and in a logical sequence	3.22	69%	Medium
Present a practical model to students during the lesson	3.09	67%	Medium
takes into account the individual abilities of the students	3.04	66%	Medium
Asks appropriate questions that stimulate thinking and creativity	2.99	64%	Medium
Uses the utilities available at the school.	2.87	62%	Medium
Provides competitive activities in light of the school's available capabilities	2.82	61%	Medium
Observes and enhances good performance and corrects faulty performance	2.56	60%	Medium
Links individual skills with new group skills	2.41	60%	Medium
Linking physical education subject to other school subjects	2.35	59%	Low
The overall score of 3.66 is an average	3.66	66%	Medium

Table 4: Arithmetic averages and percentages of teaching competencies of physical education teachers in the field of teaching methods

Adequacy of the field of implementation	Mean	The percentage	The score
Diversity of teaching methods according to educational and educational objective	3.46	82%	Is very large
The use of methods that adopt the principle of gradation from easy to difficult	3.42	80%	High
Using modern methods that take into account the safety of students	3.40	77%	Great
The use of modern methods in teaching motor skills	3.31	75%	Intermediate
Using methods that give the largest possible amount of direct and indirect results	2.89	74%	Medium
Using methods that allow students to express their opinions freely	2.77	73%	medium
Using methods that direct students' activities and actually involve them in the lesson	2.61	71%	Medium
Use of methods that help to raise motivation among students	2.57	68%	Medium
Using methods that take into account the principle of individual differences among students	2.41	66%	Medium
Using methods that gain students the desired habits for the benefit of the individual and society	2.38	62%	Medium
Determination of appropriate pre-evaluation methods	2.29	61%	Medium
Determination of appropriate formative evaluation methods	2.20	58%	Low
Determining the educational values and concepts that students should acquire	2.15	56%	Low
The overall score of 3.32 is significant	3.32	70%	Intermediate

physical education teachers in the Western Mountain region from their point of view within the field of teaching methods.

Table 4 shows the arithmetic averages and percentages of the responses of physical education teachers to each paragraph of the teaching methods field, as the percentage of teachers in this field was very large for the first and second paragraphs, as the percentage of responses ranged between (80% - 82%) While paragraphs (3 to 7) came in a large column according to the hypothesis criterion, where the percentage of responses ranged between (71% - 77%) and was moderate on paragraphs (8-12), as the percentage of responses reached 62% respectively. - 68%), while it was few in the last paragraph, which was its percentage (58%), the overall score for the field as a whole was large, and the percentage of responses reached (70%).

Through the analysis of the table it is evident the interest of physical education teachers in the teaching competencies of the field of teaching methods, their diversity and their suitability to the levels of students. To a large degree, the teachers' interest in the methodological courses in the field and periodically undertaken by the educational activity and inspection departments in order to raise the efficiency of teachers

And developing their capabilities in addition to the incentive system adopted in some departments

provided by education directorates, which motivated the increase in giving and good work.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Intensification of teaching and methodological courses by educational supervisors that have applied aspects for teacher development
2. Urging teachers to use modern means and educational technology, and holding exchange visits between teachers
3. Urging educational researchers to conduct field studies related to the planning and evaluation competencies of physical education teachers.
4. Urging educational supervisors to conduct professional research in physical education and on academic and professional development on their own due to its importance and link to professional growth in physical education teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Tawfiq Merhi and Muhammad Mahmoud Al-Hailah; General teaching methods: (Amman, Dar Al-Masirah, 2002).
2. Jaber Abdel-Hamid Jaber; Teaching skills: (Cairo, Dar Al Nahda, 1985).
3. Hassan Sayed Moawad; Teaching Methods in Mathematical Education: (Cairo, Dar Al Fikr Al Arabi, 1982).
4. Hussein Jamea and others; Analysis of verbal interaction inside the study room and its applications in Kuwait (Journal of the Institute of Education for Teachers, Kuwait, No. 36, 1982).

5. Zakia Ibrahim Kamel and two others; Teaching Methods in Physical Education, Basics in Physical Education, Part 1, 1st Edition: (Alexandria, Dar Al-Wafaa for the World of Printing and Publishing, 2007).
6. Abd al-Mu'ti Muhammad al-Sabbagh; The extent to which teachers of community colleges in Jordan know about the educational technological competencies and their practice of these competencies and the degree of their necessity for them: (Unpublished Master Thesis, Yarmouk University, Irbid, 1999).
7. Abd al-Hamid Abd al-Majeed al-Baldawi; Methods of Statistics and Business Administration with the Use of SPSS Program, First Edition: (Oman, Wael Publishing House, 2009).
8. Omar Sheikh and others; On the level of Jordan's performance in the international study of science and mathematics (National Center for Research and Development Series Studies 8, Amman, 1991).
9. Fouad Al-Khasawneh and Strak Riad; Evaluating the performance of educational supervisors in Jordan in light of their tasks and modern supervisory trends, 1st Edition: (Amman, Weal Publishing House, 2004).
10. Mamd Saeed Azmy; Methods of developing and implementing the physical education lesson in the basic education stage between theory and practice: (Egypt, Alexandria University, 1996).
11. Muhammad Abdul-Aal Al-Nuaimi and Hassan Yassin Tohme; Applied Statistics, Edition 1: (Amman, Weal Publishing House, 2008).
12. Ahmed Nasreddin Radwan; Introduction to Measurement in Physical Education and Sports, Edition 1: (The Book Center for Publishing, Cairo, 2006).
13. Kamal Abdul-Aziz Amina Abbas; Teaching Competencies Priorities and Training Needs for Middle School Teachers and General Education in the State of Qatar from the Teachers' and Mentors' Point of View, College of Education Journal (20).